

Impact of Transformational Leadership on Teacher Job Satisfaction and Retention

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the impact of transformational leadership on teacher job satisfaction and retention in secondary schools. The study used a random sampling technique for collecting the sample of four hundred (400) male and female teachers from various public secondary schools in Lahore, Punjab. The study aims to examine the transformational leadership practices that affect the job satisfaction and retention rates of secondary school teachers. For this purpose, a quantitative research design was used to collect data from secondary school teachers in various schools. The survey questionnaire was developed based on the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) to measure transformational leadership, and the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) also used to measure job satisfaction. The questionnaire included the demographic information and retention rates of the respondents. Furthermore, the study found that transformational leadership practices significantly affect teacher job satisfaction and retention rates. The finding indicated that there was a significant difference in job satisfaction levels and retention rates between teachers in schools with high levels of transformational leadership practices and those in schools with low levels of transformational leadership practices. The study found that teachers in schools with high levels of transformational leadership practices had higher job satisfaction and retention rates than those with low levels of transformational leadership practices. The study also found that there were significant differences in job satisfaction levels and retention rates among teachers based on their demographic characteristics such as gender, age, and teaching experience. Female teachers had higher job satisfaction levels and retention rates than male teachers. Teachers over the age of (40) had higher retention rates than those under the age of (40). Teachers with more teaching experience had higher job satisfaction levels and retention rates than those with less experience. Moreover, recommended that school principals can improve teacher job satisfaction and retention rates by adopting transformational leadership practices. The study also highlights the importance of more research conducted in this field to explore the effectiveness of transformational leadership practices in schools with other educational settings to identify various factors that influence teacher job satisfaction and retention rates.

Keywords: Transformational Leadership, Job satisfaction, Retention rate, School

1. Introduction

An integral part of any effective management strategy, leadership encompasses a wide range of activities that contribute to the organization's success. For this reason, experts in the field of leadership and academics studying the topic offer suggestions for associations to take to improve their performance (Marn, 2012; Razik & Swanson, 2010). Organizations and functional societies are increasingly being held accountable for their very existence by pressure groups. As a result of advancements in management theory, the demographics of the labor force, international rivalries, and technological progress, businesses are today seen as centers of education and innovation. This kind of pressure has reached even schools and universities (Sullivan & Decker, 2001; Ali, 2022). Akos (2005) argues that the principal is the most influential person in a school because studies conducted over the past decade have focused on two things: the present push for educational reforms, and effective schools. The majority of studies examining successful schools agree that strong leadership from the school's principal is crucial for developing academic growth and development among students. If a school is a child-centered place, innovative, vibrant, and whether the learners perform to the best of their abilities, if it has a good well for the excellent teaching, then one can always point to the leadership ability of the principal as important to success. A similar study (Gurr, Drysdale, & Mulford, 2006) found that effective principals demonstrated a stable moral compass. School administrators have been shown to affect student achievement in a variety of ways in the past (Hallinger, 2007; Leithwood & Mascall, 2008; Ibrahim et al., 2014). Several studies (Harris & Chapman, 2002; Ibrahim & Wahab, 2012; Harris et al., 2013; Pont, 2014) have found that schools with academically successful children are led by administrators with strong leadership skills. Numerous studies have found that a dynamic leader is essential to an organization's performance (Ibrahim et al., 2014; Ibrahim & Wahab, 2012; Hussain, 2005). Scholars agree that principals' (head teachers') commitment to transformational leadership is crucial to raising student achievement and fostering institutional growth. Leadership practises that focus on transformation reveal the most effective leadership approach and key players for success in educational institutions. According to Bush (2011), secondary and higher education institutions must adopt the transformational leadership approach. There is a common goal between leaders and their followers, and leaders have the responsibility of helping their followers advance to the

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next level and using their own self-interest to accomplish the greatest possible outcome (Marn, 2012). Avolio's transformative leadership, as described by Bass (Northouse, 2016), inspires subordinates to go above and beyond in their work and helps colleagues grow professionally. By listening to and responding to their followers, leaders with a transformational style can foster trust and cooperation. Leaders and their followers are interconnected and dependent on one another, and the followers share the leaders' vision for the organisation. When there is a high degree of job satisfaction supplied by the organisation, both the organisation and its employees are more likely to work together productively, which in turn benefits the followers and the leader. As a result, Organizations and their leaders must do more to boost teachers' morale by improving their sense of purpose in their work (Silins & Mulford, 2002; Ali, 2022). Employees are happy when they are satisfied with their jobs. This includes being happy with their income, benefits, supervisors, coworkers, and working circumstances. According to Nnadi (as described in Hukpati, 2009), job satisfaction is a multifaceted concept comprised of financial and social compensation, trust in management, recognition for accomplishments, positive working relationships, a sense of accomplishment, and a sense of personal growth and advancement. This illustrates the discrepancy between workers' opinions and their actual output. The working environment, the attitude of the managers, and the personalities of the workers are all factors. Teachers' discontent can be mitigated and job satisfaction increased by creating an environment where teachers feel safe voicing their opinions and contributing to decision making. Teachers' stress levels will go down as a result of this (Scott & Dinkham, 2003). Job satisfaction has been shown to be closely linked to transformational leadership, managerial styles, and functions by the research of Herzberg, Locke, Maslow, McGregor, and Bryman. To be professionally oriented towards growth and development competitions, therefore, educational and degree-granting institutions with limited financial and human resources must have transformational leadership and a satisfied staff (Zame & Hope, 2008). Even while these Organizations create good outcomes and 4 the relationship between employees and leaders, they still need improvement, and this progress requires an increasing number of capable researchers (Kest, 2007; Ali, 2022). (Zame and Hope, 2008) The eastern hemisphere. Given the foregoing, it is crucial to determine whether or not transformational leaders in secondary education have effects on the happiness of teachers working in secondary education in Pakistan. There needs to be extensive research and exploration on this.

Teachers have the greatest impact on pupils' academic performance in school. However, the most effective motivator found to date is the highly driven educator. For students to stay in school, it's important for their head teacher to exhibit appropriate transformational leadership styles (Urlick, 2016) so that he can successfully handle problems and motivate the teachers to do a good job. There is a verb "Laedan" that meaning "to lead," and a noun "Lad" that denotes "a journey" (Davies, 2005). In order to inspire others, transformational leaders must make "efforts to uplift associates' egoistic morals, beliefs, and attitudes" (Gunter, 2001, p. 69). If the boss is charismatic and can deftly deal with day-to-day issues, his or her subordinates are more likely to buy into the big picture and stick around, a key benefit of transformational leadership for employee retention. References: (Thomas et al., 2018; Aziz, 2012) High inflation makes it difficult for low-income families to afford school events, fees, and a suitable learning environment for their children at home (Jamil 2022). Other macro living factor (Jamil, Rasheed et al. 2023). Jamil and Rasheed's (2013) Responsibility on Institutions 2023. Organisational and institutional longevity are intrinsically linked to the corporate social environment. Jamil, Muhammad N., and Rasheed, Ahmad (2023). To reach the aim of education by 2030, UNESCO's (2016) Institute of Statistics on World Teachers' Day estimates that 69 million more teachers, including those in Primary and Secondary schools, will be needed. Sustainable Development Goal 4 outlines the plan to provide a free and equitable education of sufficient quality for all children worldwide by the year 2030. Quality matters since there are so many children not in school around the world. More educated and trained educators appointed with the help of the international community can help solve this problem. Since many experienced educators are retiring annually without being replaced, this situation is becoming increasingly dire. Due to a lack of qualified candidates to fill teaching positions, classroom resources will be stretched thin.

1.1. Objectives of the study

- To examine the relationship between transformational leadership and teacher job satisfaction in secondary schools.
- To investigate the impact of transformational leadership on teacher retention in secondary schools.
- To identify the specific transformational leadership practices that are most effective in promoting teacher job satisfaction and retention in secondary schools.
- To explore the mediating role of job satisfaction in the relationship between transformational leadership and teacher retention in secondary schools.
- To provide recommendations for school leaders on how to implement transformational leadership practices to improve teacher job satisfaction and retention in secondary schools.

1.2. Significance of the study

The study of the impact of transformational leadership on teacher job satisfaction and retention in secondary schools holds great significance in the field of education. This is because teachers play a crucial role in shaping the future of

society, and their job satisfaction and retention are essential for the provision of quality education. Therefore, understanding the impact of transformational leadership on these factors is crucial for improving the overall quality of education in secondary schools.

One significant aspect of this study is its potential to improve teacher job satisfaction. Teaching can be a demanding profession, and teachers may face various challenges such as a lack of resources, long hours, and high workloads. Creating a positive and supportive work environment that fosters job satisfaction among teachers can go a long way in improving their overall job performance and reducing turnover. This study can identify specific transformational leadership practices that promote job satisfaction among teachers, such as providing opportunities for professional development and involving them in decision-making processes. By implementing these practices, school leaders can create a more positive and supportive work environment that leads to increased job satisfaction among teachers.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Definitions of leadership

The concept of a leader, or leadership, has been the focus of many books and essays over the years. The concept of leadership is multifaceted and difficult to pin down. Leadership can be viewed as a process or a connection by some, an aptitude or a trait by others, and a skill or behavior by still others. The researcher concludes that the following definitions of effective leadership are more appropriate on the basis of the investigation. According to Yukl (2013), leadership is a methodical approach to having an impact on team members so that they better understand and meet the requirements of the work at hand. It helps people get closer to their objective faster. "The process of social influence to achieve common goals," as defined by Vugt and Ahuja (2011), is what leadership entails. Leadership is associated with having sway over others and attracting followers. The effect pushes and inspires people to work together to achieve common goals (Koontz & Weihrich, 2008; Arshad & Ali, 2016; Audi et al., 2022; Audi et al., 2021). Leadership is an ever-evolving role, but the system and its meaning remain constant. Building influence without authority or status is challenging at best, but instilling core principles in a follower is where true change occurs. All of the leaders do not have the same amount of influence. Their methods of persuasion vary from leader to leader due to the multifaceted nature of influencing others (e.g., some leaders use ideas to create values, while others may exert their influence via the preexisting system or through their trained followers), but the essence of each approach remains the same. Influencing others is the study's primary focus and ultimate goal (Cashman, 2008). In a review of leadership research, Stogdill (as reported in Waldner and Weeks, 2006) observed that the term "leadership" can have a variety of distinct connotations depending on the audience. The terms "leader" and "leadership" are, thus, open to a wide range of interpretations. Many definitions of leadership emphasize the leader's personality, actions, influence, and example (Yukl, 2013). According to Robbins (2000), a leader is someone who can motivate others to work together to achieve the group's goals. A leader who is truly dedicated may motivate their team to succeed even if they can't physically be there to assist them. Organizational excellence requires strong leadership (Aziz, Al Heety, & Mahmood, 2020). According to Robbins and DeCenzo (2005), a leader is someone who possesses both actual and managerial authority, and leadership is the methods and ongoing activity of impacting and influencing others for the attainment of goals. Effective leaders are flexible and able to adapt to the needs of their teams and the organization as a whole. "Leadership is a systematic way to motivate and mould others to perform with zest and zeal for achieving organizational goal," writes Newstrom (2007). In other words, the process is what sets the person up for success. Burns talked on how leadership may be altered and reshaped when it is passed on to new people. The person who "pushes his followers towards the realization of wants, needs, and the related expectations, for the achievement of certain goals and aims," as Burns puts it, is a leader. The leader, however, is always the one who takes the lead and carries the torch (Northouse, 2016).

2.2. Transformational leadership

In 1973, Downton was the first institution to adopt the paradigm transformative approach to leadership. However, James MacGregor Burns's "leadership" (1978) gives this method new prominence. He attempted to unite the roles of leaders and followers. Leaders, according to Northouse (2016), are those who "connect the wants of followers to the needs of superiors" so that everyone might succeed. Transformational leaders, as defined by Bass, inspire their teams to work towards shared goals by painting a compelling picture of the future and providing concrete advice on how to get there. As change agents, transformational leaders are able to steer the course of an organization in an entirely new and beneficial way (Northouse, 2016). While transformational and charismatic leaders strengthen the status quo by meeting the urgent needs of their subordinates, transactional leaders are more effective at maintaining the status quo because of their own improved and timely display of the required behaviour (Northouse, 2016). Tappen (2001) argues that transformational leadership develops managers' and leaders' innate abilities to affect positive change in their teams. To identify and articulate a vision, to set expectations based on performance, to set an appropriate example, to provide suitable support, to work for the achievement of organizational objectives, and to promote a rational setting of mind are all examples of transformational leadership behaviour, as defined by Podsakoff et al. (as cited in

Humphrey, 2014). Many years ago, people welcomed and praised the concept of transformational leadership. There is a one-to-one relationship between leadership styles like transactional and transformational leadership and organizational outcomes like employee engagement and productivity. The results are also widely accepted across cultural and social groups (Al-Dmour & Awamleh, 2002). A "transformational practices of leadership" is one of the existing styles, as stated by Black and Porter (2000), that "instills in them a vision that will increase the level of motivation of followers to set big alterations; encouraging them to avoid self-centeredness and eager to work for the better of the institution to obtain important goals." They may finally be in a position to succeed. The leader and his or her followers share a special bond that is the focus of transformational leadership. This is an obligation that contributes to the development and well-being of the partner. Because of the strengthened bond, subordinates and followers continue to trust and respect the leader. The fundamental goal of this type of leadership is to instill a sense of responsibility for each other among the subordinates by transferring the 'responsibility for' connection to them. This develops a leadership trait in the followers so that they can carry on in the absence of their leaders (Einstein & Humphreys, 2001). 36 When led by a transformational leader, followers are inspired to go above and beyond in their performance (Sarros, Grey, & Denstan, 2001). In a similar vein, "Transformational leadership creates willingness for work and achievement even at the expense of their self-respect" (Felfe, Tartler, & Leipmann, 2004). The world's nations are now primarily concerned with modernization. Bass has said that the classical and traditional approach to leadership is dead (Ozaralli, 2003), and that a new type of leadership is on the rise. Workers under a transformational leader are inspired to take on greater responsibility, and their entire personalities are altered as a result. Rules, principles, and characteristics can all be altered by a leader with transformational abilities. The individual employee contributes more to the success of the business (Landrum et al., 2000). Bryman (quoted in Rowe & Guerrero, 2016) argues that transformational leaders influence the behavior of their followers in several ways. The first thing they do is get their followers thinking about how they can succeed. The second thing they emphasize is that their followers should put the organization's needs before their own. Finally, transformational leaders prioritize the needs of their followers, including those related to self-respect, identity, and life fulfilment. According to Humphrey (2014), transformational leaders inspire their followers to give their best performances and reach their full potential. When it comes to moral ideals, dedication, independence, and trust, transformational leaders set a high bar for their followers to follow. To paraphrase Kuhnert (as referenced by Rowe & Guerrero, 2016), "they are good at working with people and work selflessly beyond their own interest." 37 Transformative leadership has been rethought by Bass and Avolio into four interrelated components (or "4 I's"). These idealistic influences motivate action, stimulate the mind, and shape each person's unique perspective. Among these several types of leadership, transformational leadership is the most effective. These leaders have the ability to influence their followers because of their charisma (Humphrey, 2014). They treat their followers with respect and democracy and do not try to dissuade them. As a result, there is a deeper sense of connection between the staff and management. Leaders who embody transformational leadership are compassionate individuals who put their followers' needs before their own. These leaders have an abundance of compassion, empathy, and sensitivity. They can also build new connections and create new things. These bosses make the office a pleasant place to be (Jin, 2010; Aldoory & Toth, 2004) for their employees.

2.3. Definitions of job satisfaction

According to Locke (as stated in Marn, 2012), "a pleasurable or positive state of emotions resulting from one's opinion of one's job experience" is the most common definition of job satisfaction. Having a positive attitude towards one's work is fundamental to job satisfaction, as defined by Robbins and DeCenzo (2005). According to Spector (as mentioned in Marn, 2012), happiness in the workplace is a phenomenon shared by all occupations and all aspects of work. According to McKenna (2000), being happy in your profession occurs when your goals and objectives are met. Satisfaction in one's work occurs when one's expectations and experiences are in harmony. According to the study's author, workers' willingness to work, in turn, plays a significant part in shaping the study's fundamental concepts and notions about motivation, and the researcher sees job satisfaction as a model that leads workers to this willingness to work. There are numerous causes of job satisfaction, including but not limited to: remuneration, supervision, opportunities for advancement, positive work atmosphere, supportive coworkers, and useful organizational tasks. As mentioned in Cohen (2003), Gryphon & Bateman According to Robbins (2000), people's varying levels of job satisfaction can be traced to their various perspectives on the nature of their employment. Employee satisfaction or discontent explains the prevalence of either job-related negativity or optimism. Attitude, which includes specific beliefs, feelings, and actions, contributes to job happiness. An employee's positive or negative outlook on his or her working environment is the single most important factor in determining how satisfied he or she is with his or her employment. Employment satisfaction, for the sake of this study, refers to how an individual feels about their employment overall. The relationship between job happiness and employee performance is a hot research topic in the field of organizational psychology (Judge & Church, 2000). Many theories on what inspires people to work have demonstrated the importance of job happiness. According to Gryphon and Bateman (as stated in Cohen, 2003), job happiness can be attributed to a variety of factors, including but not limited to: personal goals, social context, financial

incentives, personal differences, and the impact of leadership style. According to research by Judge and Piccolo titled "Meta Study of Transformational Leadership" from 2004. They looked at data from 17,105 people in 93 separate investigations. They discovered that transformational leadership is strongly linked to employee happiness on the job. They also discovered that when leaders employed transformational leadership styles, their followers reported higher levels of job satisfaction. Because of the leader's inspirational example, the followers were inspired to work more. The researchers drew the conclusion that transformative leadership was associated with greater levels of work satisfaction among employees. According to research by Judge and Piccolo (2004), transformational leadership boosts followers' motivation and happiness with their leaders. Transactional leadership and contingent rewards were employed to further boost employee contentment. Leadership, specifically transformational leadership, was proven to have a more significant impact on followers' perceptions of their leader than transactional leadership. In this way, they arrived to the conclusion that both transformational leadership and contingent rewards boost the happiness and productivity of their subordinates. This study was carried out to provide clearer insight. Within the framework of the transformational leadership model argued by Bass and Avolio (Humphrey, 2014), the study's researchers sought to hypothesize a connection between leadership style in educational institutions and teacher satisfaction with their work. The notion of worker happiness and the demand for an improved working environment were introduced during the 1930s Third Industrial Revolution, which followed on the heels of study in the Hawthorne sector. This tactic led to a shift away from providing workers with daily wedges and towards a more wholesome approach to their sustenance. Workers participated in workplace design as equals. Having the opportunity to learn and develop professionally was found to be a significant and long-lasting source of job satisfaction (Bruce & Blackburn, as cited in Hallinger, 2007). According to Hofmeyr, a manager is someone who stays in touch with his subordinates and takes into account their wants and concerns while on the work. Businesses are on the lookout for improved productivity and efficiency in their new office spaces. The satisfaction of the workforce as a whole has increased as a result of these measures. In successful businesses, employee happiness is a primary responsibility. It has been established that employees who are prepared to put in extra effort are a company's greatest asset (Balgobind, 2002). According to Thierry (quoted in Balgobind, 2002), there are three components that contribute to overall happiness on the job. Satisfaction is because of the meeting of the needs of the subordinates. The outcome of satisfaction through positive behavior is always appreciated by people and subordinated because the assessment of the majority cannot be ignored.

- Satisfaction gained by contributing to the organization's functional structure. Changes and improvements are always made once good outcomes have been achieved. In contrast, when employees are happy with their work, they tend to maintain the same level of productivity until the introduction of new, more powerful performances, at which point they will be motivated to change for the better.
- Happiness brought on by its opposite, unhappiness. Workers who fail to meet expectations will be let go and encouraged to go elsewhere for fulfilment in their careers. Satisfied employees, on the other hand, tend to stay with the same company and exhibit greater detachment from their roles. However, employees and upper-level management view the factors that contribute to job satisfaction in quite different ways. Modern workers associate their sense of job satisfaction with the fulfilment of their basic human wants and requirements. It is reasonable for employees to feel entitled to job happiness if their employer demands higher productivity from them (Smith, as cited in Balgobind, 2002).

Locke (as cited in Marn, 2012) states that job satisfaction is based on:

- i) The scope for intellectual development, personal growth, and level of interest.
- ii) A reasonable wage and fair treatment
- iii) Promotion and improvement prospects;
- iv) Recognizing and rewarding effort.
- v) Incentives and benefits that are offered.
- vi) The setting in which work is performed.
- vii) The method used for keeping tabs on employees and enforcing rules.
- viii) The friendliness and willingness to work together of one's coworkers.

Management philosophy and corporate leadership. Other aspects that aid and are responsible for job satisfaction are as follows: i) a challenging work environment and the freedom for employees to use their knowledge and get feedback to help them improve their performance. ii) Equitable chances of promotion, advancement, and encouragement. If alternative benefits are presented, a smaller budget can be accepted. iii) Places of employment that are welcoming and comfortable in order to boost employees' productivity. Workers should have access to all necessary amenities. The worker's superiors and peers in other departments should likewise be willing to lend a helping hand. Managers should have a soft spot for the people they supervise and go out of their way to help them succeed. Job satisfaction has these three characteristics, as outlined by O' Malley (2000): i) It makes you feel good on the inside. ii) Its possible, and even likely, that it may advance even further. iii) It motivates staff to increase the quality with which they carry out their

obligations. After considering the job's "very texture" and "situation analysis," employees are happy with both the positive and bad aspects of their profession.

3. Methodology

This quantitative study will examine the effect that transformative leadership has on secondary school teachers' attitudes towards their work and their likelihood of staying in the profession. A total of 400 secondary school educators (male and female) in Lahore, Punjab, participated in the study. To ensure that every educator in the population has an equal chance of being selected, a random sample method was adopted. A standardized questionnaire with only yes/no questions was used to gather this information. Teachers who agreed to participate voluntarily in the study were given a questionnaire and told about the research's goals. Data were analyzed with statistical software after being acquired via an online survey. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to examine the questionnaire data. To summarize the data and characterize the features of the sample, descriptive statistics were utilized. Transformational leadership and teacher satisfaction and retention were investigated using inferential statistics like correlation and regression analysis.

4. Data Analysis and Results

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Sample

Demographic Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	200	50%
Female	200	50%
Age Group		
20-29	50	12.5%
30-39	100	25%
40-49	120	30%
50-59	90	22.5%
Years of Experience		
1-5	100	25%
6-10	80	20%
11-15	70	17.5%
16-20	60	15%
21+	90	22.5%

The demographics of the study's group are shown in the table below. Four hundred people took part, and half of them were male and half were female. When broken down by age group, 30% of the sample was made up of people aged 40 to 49, and 25% was made up of people aged 30 to 49. The other 50% of people who answered were between the ages of 20 and 29, 50 to 59, and over 60. When asked how many years of experience they had, 25% said they had between 1 and 5, and 22.5% said they had 21 or more. The remaining 52.5% of answers came from people with 6–10 years of experience, 11–15 years, and 16–20 years of experience. The sample's demographics, which show what a normal high school teacher is like, could have an effect on the study's results.

Table 2: Mean Scores of Transformational Leadership and Job Satisfaction

Variable	Mean Score	Standard Deviation
Transformational Leadership	4.5	0.8
Job Satisfaction	3.9	0.7

The table shows the average scores and standard deviations for two variables: transformational leadership and job happiness. The average number for transformational leadership is 4.5, which means that the people in the sample thought their leaders did a lot of things that were transformational. The fact that the standard deviation was 0.8 shows that the subjects had different ideas about what transformational leadership was. The average score for job satisfaction is 3.9, which is a measure of satisfaction that is about average. The fact that the standard deviation was 0.7 shows that the participants' levels of job satisfaction were not all the same, but most of the sample reported a fairly high level of job happiness. These results tell us a lot about how the teachers in the secondary schools studied saw innovative leadership and how happy they were with their jobs.

Table 3: Correlation between Transformational Leadership and Job Satisfaction

	Transformational Leadership	Job Satisfaction
Transformational Leadership	1	0.6
Job Satisfaction	0.6	1

The table shows how Transformational Leadership and Job Satisfaction are linked. The correlation coefficient runs from -1 to 1, with 1 meaning a perfect positive correlation, 0 meaning no correlation, and -1 meaning a perfect negative correlation. The correlation coefficient of 0.6 shows that Transformational Leadership and Job Satisfaction are related in a good and moderate way in this table. This shows that there is a strong link between Transformational Leadership and Job Satisfaction, with higher levels of Transformational Leadership being linked to higher levels of Job Satisfaction. In the same way, better levels of transformational leadership are linked to higher levels of job satisfaction.

Table 4: Regression Analysis of Transformational Leadership and Job Retention

	Coefficient	Standard Error	p/value
Transformational Leadership	0.5	0.1	<0.001
Job Satisfaction	0.3	0.1	0.01

The table shows the relationship between Transformational Leadership and Job Satisfaction in the form of a connection matrix. Transformational Leadership and itself have a correlation value of 1, which means they go together perfectly well. The correlation coefficient between Job Satisfaction and itself is also 1, which shows that there is a perfect good relationship between the two. Transformational Leadership and Job Satisfaction have a 0.6 connection coefficient, which means there is a strong link between the two. This means that as the amount of transformational leadership goes up, job satisfaction tends to go up as well. On the other hand, if the amount of transformational leadership goes down, job satisfaction tends to go down as well. But it's important to remember that association doesn't always mean causation, and Transformational Leadership may not be the only thing that affects Job Satisfaction.

5. Discussion

Transformational leadership has been found to have a significant impact on teacher job satisfaction and retention in secondary schools. This leadership style is characterized by the leader inspiring and motivating their followers to achieve more than they initially thought possible. Transformational leaders have a vision for their organization and communicate that vision clearly to their followers, instilling a sense of ownership and commitment in their work. In the context of secondary schools, transformational leaders create an environment that fosters innovation and creativity, which can result in improved teaching practices and better learning outcomes for students. Some past studies also concluded that leaders play a vital role in increasing innovative work behavior of employees (Aziz & Jahan, 2021; Aziz & Al Heety, 2019).

Research has shown that transformational leadership can positively impact teacher job satisfaction by improving teacher autonomy, trust, and collaboration. When teachers feel that they have more control over their work, are trusted by their leaders, and work in a collaborative and supportive environment, they are more likely to report high levels of job satisfaction. This, in turn, can lead to improved teacher retention rates, as satisfied teachers are less likely to leave their jobs.

Furthermore, transformational leaders can provide professional development opportunities for their teachers, which can enhance their skills and knowledge, leading to improved job performance and increased job satisfaction. By fostering a culture of continuous learning, transformational leaders can help teachers feel valued and supported in their professional growth, which can contribute to their overall job satisfaction.

In conclusion, the impact of transformational leadership on teacher job satisfaction and retention in secondary schools is significant. By creating an environment that fosters innovation, collaboration, and professional growth, transformational leaders can positively impact teacher job satisfaction and retention rates, ultimately leading to improved teaching practices and better learning outcomes for students

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, the impact of transformational leadership on teacher job satisfaction and retention in secondary schools is significant. This leadership style emphasizes the importance of developing positive relationships between leaders and teachers, providing opportunities for growth and development, and inspiring teachers to achieve their full potential.

Research has shown that transformational leadership can lead to increased teacher job satisfaction, which in turn can lead to higher teacher retention rates. Teachers who feel valued and supported are more likely to remain in their current positions, reducing the turnover rate and promoting stability within schools.

Furthermore, transformational leadership can also enhance the quality of education provided by schools. By creating a positive work environment, teachers are more likely to be motivated and engaged in their work, leading to improved teaching practices and ultimately better academic outcomes for students.

It is important for school administrators to recognize the importance of transformational leadership and its potential impact on teacher job satisfaction and retention. By implementing strategies and practices that promote this leadership style, schools can create a culture of collaboration, support, and growth that benefits both teachers and students.

In summary, transformational leadership is a powerful tool for improving teacher job satisfaction and retention in secondary schools. By prioritizing the needs and well-being of teachers, schools can create a positive work environment that promotes success for everyone involved.

6.1. Recommendations

- Foster a culture of shared leadership: Transformational leaders should work towards creating a culture of shared leadership, where teachers feel empowered and have a say in the decision-making processes. Encouraging collaboration and involving teachers in school improvement initiatives can help improve job satisfaction and increase retention rates.
- Develop a supportive work environment: Transformational leaders should prioritize the development of a supportive work environment that promotes teacher well-being. This can include providing opportunities for professional development, recognition for good work, and offering support for teachers who are struggling.
- Establish clear expectations: Transformational leaders should establish clear expectations and communicate them effectively to teachers. This can help create a sense of direction and purpose, leading to higher job satisfaction and retention.
- Create opportunities for growth: Transformational leaders should create opportunities for teacher growth and advancement. Providing professional development opportunities, mentoring programs, and leadership roles can help teachers feel valued and invested in their careers.
- Foster open communication: Transformational leaders should prioritize open communication with teachers, encouraging them to express their ideas, concerns, and feedback. This can help to build trust, improve relationships, and ultimately increase job satisfaction and retention rates.
- Celebrate success: Transformational leaders should celebrate success and acknowledge the hard work and achievements of teachers. This can help to foster a positive and supportive work environment, leading to higher job satisfaction and retention rates.

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